

DEFINITION OF THE CONCEPTS “FOREIGN LEXEMES” AND “LOANWORDS”

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ABSTRACT

This article discusses the definition of the words "foreign lexemes" and "loanwords", gives examples of this grammatical process and the history of its origin.

INTRODUCTION

Lexical development is pervasive and contributes to the emergence of new words, the expansion of meanings, and the transformation of established ones. This is a varied and complex process operating very actively in and across different speech communities since languages in contact enable “foreign lexemes”. For example, an average English speaker would understand ‘an *origami emoji* of a *kimono*’ even if she does not know the etymology or the Japanese origin of the content words in the phrase. English as a *lingua franca* has been a source of new words for many languages though the reverse process has also meant that the English lexicon has been enriched by words from a wide range of donor languages. Although Liberman argues that ‘these are monuments to human beings’ physical mobility and mental laziness’,

loanwords add to the development of language productivity¹.

MAIN PART

The definition of “foreign lexemes” indicates a mechanism whereby a recipient language borrows morphemes, words, and phrases from a donor language. “Foreign lexemes”, according to Haspelmath (2019) refers, on the one hand, to all kinds of transfer or copying processes resulting from ‘non-native speakers imposing properties of their native language onto a recipient language’ and, on the other hand, to ‘the incorporation of foreign elements into the speakers’ native language, a synonym for ‘adoption’. However, despite the controversies surrounding the terminology posit that ‘lexical borrowing has become the established term to describe the process of the transfer of lexical material from one language (the donor, source or model language) to

¹ Aikhenvald, Alexandra. 2012. *Language Contact in Amazonia*. Oxford: Oxford University Press.

another language (the receptor or replica language)².

“Loanword” (or lexical borrowing) is here defined as a word that at some point in the history of a language entered its lexicon as a result of borrowing (or *transfer*, or *copying*). Fortunately, this definition is uncontroversial, but there are a number of things to note.

First, the term *borrowing* has been used in two different senses: (i) As a general term for all kinds of transfer or copying processes, whether they are due to native speakers adopting elements from other languages into the recipient language, or whether they result from non-native speakers imposing properties of their native language onto a recipient language. This general sense seems to be by far the most prevalent use of the term *borrowing*. But *borrowing* has also been used in a more restricted sense, (ii) “to refer to the incorporation of foreign elements into the speakers’ native language”, i.e. as a synonym of *adoption* (Thomason & Kaufman use the term *substratum interference* for ‘imposition’, and *interference* as a cover term for ‘borrowing/adoption’ and ‘substratum interference/ imposition’).

In this work, we use *borrowing* in the more common, broad sense, and the two types of borrowing, depending on whether the borrowers are native speakers or non-native speakers, are called adoption and imposition (or, equivalently, *retention*). Apart from the fact that this terminology

is more in conformity with traditional usage, it is symmetrical, and it gives us additional verbs (*adopt*, *impose*, *retain*) that can be used in a precise, technical sense. Of course, the term *borrowing* is based on a strange metaphor (after all, the donor language does not expect to receive its words back), so a term like *transfer* or *transference* would be preferable. Even better is Johanson’s (2012) term *copying*, because the transfer metaphor still suggests that the donor language loses the element in question. However, since *borrowing* is so well-established in linguistics, going back at least to the 18th century, and since the metaphor does not lead to any misunderstandings, we will continue to use it here (alongside its synonyms *transfer(ence)* and *copying*).

The language from which a loanword has been borrowed will be called the donor language, and the language into which it has been borrowed is the recipient language. (Alternative term pairs that one sometimes finds in the literature are *source language/borrowing language*, and *model language/replica language*.) The word that served as a model for the loanword will be called source word.³

Loanwords are always *words* (i.e. *lexemes*) in the narrow sense, not lexical phrases, and they are normally *unanalyzable units* in the recipient language. The corresponding source word in the donor language, by contrast, may be complex or even phrasal, but this internal structure is lost when the word enters the recipient language.³ For example, Russian has the loanword *buterbrod* ‘sandwich’, borrowed from

² Boumans, Louis & Caubet, Dominique. 2010. Modelling intrasentential codeswitching: A comparative study of Algerian/French in Algeria and Moroccan/Dutch in the Netherlands. In Owens, Jonathan (ed.), *Arabic as a minority language*, 113–180. Berlin: Mouton de Gruyter.

³ Brown, Cecil H. 2019. *Lexical acculturation in Native American languages*. New York: Oxford University Press.

German *Butter-brot* [butter-bread]. This is a transparent compound in German, but since Russian has no other words with the elements *buter* or *brod*, the Russian word is monomorphemic and not analyzable by native speakers. However, when a language borrows multiple complex words from another language, the elements may recur with a similar meaning, so that the morphological structure may be reconstituted. This is the case with the numerous Japanese loans based on Chinese compounds. For example, Japanese borrowed *kokumin* 'citizen' from Chinese *guó-mín* [country-people] (cf. Schmidt, Japanese subdatabase), but it also borrowed other words with the element *kok(u)* 'country' (e.g. *kok-ka* \$ 'nation', *koku-ō* C 'king') and other words with the element *min* 'people' (e.g. *minshū* 'population', *jūmin* ½ 'inhabitant'). As a result of these multiple borrowings, many of the original Chinese compounds are again transparent in Japanese, and can be regarded as analyzable. Similarly, in English neoclassical compounds (like *ethnography*, *ethnocracy*, *ethnology*, *gerontology*, *gerontocracy*,

Loanwords are opposed to native words, i.e. words "which we can take back to the earliest known stages of a language". But given our definition of *loanword* above, we can never exclude that a word is a loanword, i.e. that it has been borrowed at some stage in the history of the language. Thus, the status of native words is always relative to what we know about the history of a language. English *dish* goes back to Old English and has cognates in other Germanic languages (e.g. German *Tisch* 'table'), so in this sense it could be regarded as a native word (contrasting with *disk*, which was borrowed from Latin

discus in the 17th century). But we know more about the history of English than the attested forms in Old English: Proto-West Germanic **disk* has itself clearly been borrowed from Latin *discus*, so that English *dish* must count as a loanword after all. Even for words that have been reconstructed for a very ancient proto-language, such as English *mother* (from Proto-Indo-European **mātēr*) or *ten* (from **dekm*), we cannot be sure that they were not borrowed from another language at some earlier stage. Thus, we can identify loanwords, but we cannot identify "non-loanwords" in an absolute sense. A "non-loanword" is simply a word for which we have no knowledge that it was borrowed⁴.

Another important type of structural borrowing is loan meaning extension, an extremely common (and often unnoticed) process whereby a polysemy pattern of a donor language word is copied into the recipient language. For example, the English word *head* is used in a technical sense to refer to the main word in a syntactic phrase, and following this usage, the German word *Kopf* 'head' is now also used in this grammatical sense. Since such cases reproduce a semantic pattern, they also fall under structural borrowing. (Loan translations and loan meaning extensions are sometimes grouped together as *loanshifts*, i.e. lexical innovations created by purely structural borrowing; Haugen: 219.)

Finally, some authors also include loan creations among borrowings, i.e. formations that were inspired by a foreign concept but whose structure is not patterned on its expression in any way.

⁴ Ross, Malcolm. 2011. Refining Guy's sociolinguistic types of language change. *Diachronica* 8(1):119–129.

For example, the German word *Umwelt* (*Um-welt* [around-world]) was coined to render French *milieu* (*milieu* [mid-place]) 'environment'. According to Haugen, such words "may ultimately be due to contact with a second culture and its language,

but...are not strictly loans at all". However, if the meaning of the loan creation is an exact copy of the meaning of the model word, then we are dealing with clear cases of pure semantic borrowing here

References:

1. Aikhenvald, Alexandra. 2012. *Language Contact in Amazonia*. Oxford: Oxford University Press.
2. Boumans, Louis & Caubet, Dominique. 2010. Modelling intrasentential codeswitching: A comparative study of Algerian/French in Algeria and Moroccan/Dutch in the Netherlands. In Owens, Jonathan (ed.), *Arabic as a minority language*, 113–180. Berlin: Mouton de Gruyter.
3. Brown, Cecil H. 2019. *Lexical acculturation in Native American languages*. New York: Oxford University Press.
4. Haugen, Einar. 2010. The analysis of linguistic borrowing. *Language* 26:210–231.
5. Hock, Hans Henrich & Joseph, Brian D. 2016. *Language history, language change, and language relationship*. Berlin: Mouton de Gruyter.
6. Ross, Malcolm. 2011. Refining Guy's sociolinguistic types of language change. *Diachronica* 8(1):119–129.
7. Sankoff, David, Poplack, Shana and Vanniarajan, Swathi. 2010. The case of the nonce loan in Tamil. *Language variation and change* 2:71–101.